

Demand response approaches in a research project versus a real business

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ABSTRACT

Demand response through Demand Aggregation is part of the energy transition towards a green and distributed system. Although the market is open in most European countries, its practical implementation is not much successful yet. In the last decade, research presented different options to deal with demand response and aggregation. This paper compares the benefits and limitations of strategies implemented from a research perspective and the strategy followed by a recently created company to see which of the advances in research are currently useful from a business perspective. The study presents a novel decision matrix to evaluate demand response strategies. Results show that there are technical limitations in current Energy Management Systems that need to be taken into account when developing demand aggregation platforms. In addition, the study highlights the importance to propose a simple and scalable solution to allow consumers to participate actively in electricity markets and create a success business model.

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1. Introduction

Renewable energy sources (RES) as distributed energy resources (DER), with photovoltaic (PV) panels in the first place, are leading the energy transition in the world [1]. However, they alone will hardly find a way to success because of their inherent limitations, such as the dependency on weather conditions and the variability of their production [2]. They need to collaborate with other technologies and services to soften or eliminate their limits [3].

Being RES closer to consumption points and being harder (or even contradictory) to control, grid balancing techniques found a suitable dance partner in demand response (DR) frameworks [4]. This is, grid balancing services are shifting from the continuous adaptation of the generation to consumption towards a change in the demand for the same purpose using similar approaches to VPP [5].

DR is gaining relevance in Europe; directives such as the European Energy Efficiency Directive (2012/27/EU) or the recent 4th winter package “Clean Energy for All Europeans” enhance the incorporation of DR in electricity markets. DR strategies, firstly

incorporated in U.K., France, Finland, or Belgium, are now being deployed to most countries that had not yet introduced this possibility, such as the late incorporation of DR in the Spanish electricity market [6].

However, DR has still many barriers to overcome [7], like the minimum bid size, which asks for a certain amount of energy (in the order of thousands of kWh). This impedes the participation of individual buildings (and even more residential households) in these services. That is the moment when the figure of a Demand Aggregator (DA) enters into play. The role of the DA is to coordinately modify the consumption patterns of buildings in its portfolio in a way that the additive contribution of each one allows it to globally reach the necessary amount of energy that presents a significant impact on the electricity grid [8]. The ability of consumers to adapt their consumption is called demand-side flexibility. Demand-side flexibility can be used either through behind-the-meter schemes, leading to energy efficiency, or by providing services to third parties, known as intrinsic and extrinsic demand flexibility respectively [9].

To activate this new opportunity, end-users have to be aware of their energy assets' potential. The first step is to identify the energy flexibility capacity and characteristics of the different elements within the consumption site. These elements can be classified as:

1. Fixed loads: items that do not allow any flexibility such as personal computers, TV, or cooker;

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2. Shiftable or duration differentiated loads: those that allow a change in the period or level of consumption, i.e. heating, ventilation, air conditioning (HVAC) systems, washing machines, etc.
3. Curtailable loads: those elements that allow a reduction in the load, such as in the case of some home appliances or industrial processes [10].

As the flexibility capacity of the elements differs throughout the day (or season of the year), an overall estimation of the flexibility capacity along hours needs to be estimated to accurately participate in electricity markets. The same applies to the consumption forecast, which is fundamental to establishing the baseline of the consumption site.

Additionally, to move energy efficiency measures to new revenue streams, DA needs to participate in electricity markets. To do this, an optimization algorithm that manages the DA's bidding strategy is essential. At the same time, all flexible elements should be able to respond to external signals to effectively reduce or increase consumption when asked for. Finally, there is the need to verify that the response is correctly executed.

Moreover, the organization and strategies of DAs to estimate and activate flexibility assets and the billing processes to participate in electricity markets are innumerable. Nonetheless, they can be classified into two categories according to their focus of interest:

1. System-oriented or centralized: This solution puts the focus on the needs of the System Operator (SO) and uses the flexibility offered by the DA as a distributed resource to count on in case of necessity.
2. Prosumer-oriented or distributed: Following this approach, it is the user who obtains the maximum profit by offering a service to the DA that, then, trades it in electricity markets.

At the same time, these two categories can be divided into two more generic groups: on the one hand those that use competitive algorithms to select the buildings or assets to operate [11], and on the other hand, the cooperative approaches [12], where the algorithm decides what is better for the community. The challenge is to find the balance between accuracy and maintaining a model within the workable dimensions [13]. This balance is crucial to understand the behavior and strategies of different DAs when dealing with the uncertainty of results and the risk of management [14].

Research has shown that buildings have inherent energy flexibility waiting to be managed and presented (and still presents) new ways to approach or address it by finding new assets, being more precise, or providing faster responses. On the other side, market-oriented approaches search for rapid investment return and implementation with enough accuracy and security allowing a fast penetration and enhance cash flow [15]. Current Energy Management Systems (EMS) have limited functionalities that do not respond to the minimum technical requirements needed to perform the aggregation strategy presented in the literature.

In [16] the aggregator receives plenty of information from the user to optimize its strategies, including the reward that the consumer wants to receive for each specific flexibility activation, understood as the signal that allows to go on with the change in consumption. In addition, the aggregator's strategy is based on the DSO flexibility request received during the day ahead, making the model not suited for current market design and EMSs. In [17] Golpîra and Bahramara presented a cloud-based structure to manage shiftable loads and batteries at the low voltage level, formulated as a mixed-integer problem. In this case, the model does not consider uncertainties of demand, energy prices, and renewable production, and the aggregator participates only in

the day-ahead energy market. In [18] Heinrich et al. capture nicely the difficulties in real-life demonstrations that appeared in the EcoGrid 2.0 project. In this pilot, communication between aggregators and flexible units has not always been reliable during the experiments due to different reasons. This highlights the importance for aggregators to reduce the amount of data needed and to be prepared to respond to unexpected behaviors from flexible assets.

Being that the EU markets are getting ready for the full entrance of DR and DA, it seems relevant to understand which is the gap between research and what is the market capable to do based on the interests of one another. After having worked in both areas (in research projects and in the creation of a DR spin off), the team involved in this study found out that this gap is not only caused by technology deployment but also from the purpose each type of approaches pursues (increase the knowledge or provide practical and functional solutions). For this reason, a multicriteria decision process based on the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) [19] is presented to identify why each approach follows a different direction when applying solutions.

The main contributions of this work are:

- (1) Analyze the pros and cons of different DAs' strategies presented in the literature in terms of feasibility, accuracy, and closeness to the market.
- (2) Present a decision matrix tool for demand aggregation solution evaluation, which clarifies the key aspects to consider when passing from research to business in DA.
- (3) Present and compare the demand aggregation approach performed in a Horizon 2020 project and the approach adopted by a recently created start-up.
- (4) Clarify limitations of current EMS in real-life applications.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: In Section 2 the actors in the energy flexibility paradigm are located to understand the links among them. Then, the experiences gained during the development of a DA strategy in the SABINA H2020 research project (Section 3) and the creation of the several times awarded Bamboo Energy spin-off (Section 4) are presented. Note that this study does not enter into the details of the algorithms (published and proved in previous works as explained in the following sections) but it focuses the attention on the "overall" results to evaluate its practicality. Section 5, evaluates the research and business-oriented solutions to enter the DA market, presenting a novel decision matrix tool that can be used as support for further research. Finally, Section 6 presents the conclusions of the study.

As a consequence, this study presents a success story of how what began, more than six years ago, with the initial steps of energy flexibility in a research environment, ended up with a spin-off that tackles real market business on energy management in demand response applications.

2. The position of each actor in DA

The actors involved in DR through DA are classified in different levels through the electricity grid. At the upper level, there are the actors that safeguard the state of the grid, that is, the transmission and the distribution system operators (TSO & DSO) and, in some cases, there are other entities such as the Balancing Responsible Parties (BRP) that are specifically related to balancing. On the second level, some companies trade the flexibility of their customers for grid balancing purposes (receiving a payoff from SO or BRPs) as one of the energy services offered to their clients e.g energy supply, monitoring, or management. This is where the DA should be and, in some countries, the DA has to stay under the umbrella of an energy retailer. The third level is where the users (buildings) are. Finally, the fourth level is where to find the assets

Fig. 1. Actors involved in DR through DA and their position in the system.

that are within the buildings, which are the elements, such as batteries, heating/cooling systems or electric vehicles among others, that consume energy but that are capable of changing their consumption profile and, therefore, provide energy flexibility to the system. Note that, in certain cases, such as with charging stations, assets and users might be considered the same.

Depending on the interactions between the “commercial”, “user” and “assets” levels, there are three different categorizations [14], which affect the communications between the elements in each level and the final configuration:

1. Retailer: the DA provides a flat rate with no additional incentive for the user.
2. Nash Bargaining Game: Cooperation by dividing the benefits.
3. Stackelberg Game: The aggregator decides unilaterally anticipating the prosumer's reaction.

Thus, depending on who takes the responsibility of changing the consumption pattern, the communication goes from one to another element between levels. For instance, as shown in Fig. 1, the DA might communicate with the flexibility assets directly, falling into the Stackelberg Game as in the work from Olivella et al. [20] or Tang et al. [21] that controlled all the flexibility assets (batteries, electric vehicles, heaters, etc.) of the building directly. This approach is also known as Load Direct Control (LDC). On the other side, the communication flows would be from the DA at the commercial level to the EMS in the building at the user level when falling in the Nash Bargaining Game categories, as in the works from Hurtado et al. [12] or Behboodi et al. [22].

However, several crossovers might occur between these categorizations in terms of communications. The contracts between levels might indeed affect the communications, but what forces the communications is not just the element taking the decisions but also the one that activates the flexibility assets. For instance, in the work by Iria et al. [23], the DA had a perfect knowledge of the reality of the flexibility assets, so the DA knew whom to ask for flexibility. However, the element deciding what to do once the activation was raised is the EMS, which should coincide with what the DA expected to occur but it is not mandatory.

The DA can interact with the system in multiple markets. Correa-Florezet et al. presented a DA that interacted with three different entities: the wholesale market with day-ahead estimations, the DSO for constraint management and a local flexibility market

to provide response to flexibility bids to the DSO [24]. These interactions should also take special care of the real time stochasticity and ramping (as in frequency regulation markets, for instance) not only for the decision processes but also for the operational ones [25] and could be solved by using a microgrid controller that considers grid constraints, schedules, costs, number of bids, and the requests from the service provider, the DSO or other independent system operators [26].

Therefore, the DA computation efforts may go beyond the energy management of buildings' flexibility and look upwards to the interactions with the grid-level actors. In this sense, there are multiple bidding strategies to enable the participation of DA in electricity markets, being the “price taker” the simplest of the approaches, since the DA decides only the amount of energy, like in the work from Iria et al. in [27] where the decision variable is the volume of flexibility offered.

Since bidding is usually performed hours before the execution, different uncertainty sources, such as consumption, on-site DER generation, market prices, or flexibility activations, can worsen the solution. With the purpose to reduce uncertainty, some algorithms consider stochastic events, which improve economical performances by up to 22% in comparison to deterministic approaches [28]. Nevertheless, working with uncertainty adds computational complexity to the bidding process, making the problem unable to solve for a big number of flexibility sources. However, clustering or scenario reduction strategies reduce the size of the problem without compromising the solution [27]. Moreover, if the DA makes coordinated offers in different markets, the optimization problem gets even more complex [29], although economic benefits increase thanks to the multi-market participation [30].

As nicely summarized by Hamwi et al. [31], the optimization problem deals with two branches, one for costs and the other for revenues, that should end up in positive value so the DR business model has sense. While the literature is focused on finding new solutions for the bidding strategies and real-time management of flexibility sources, revenues for DA and flexibility providers depend principally on the characteristics of the site, the business model adopted, and the national-specific market requirements [7]. Costs can be divided into five main categories, and can be Capital expenditures (CAPEX) or Operating expenses (OPEX):

1. Communications (CAPEX): DR programs need a bi-directional channel between the flexibility provider and

the DA to communicate the current consumption of the site and receive flexibility activation orders. The communication channel could also include further functionalities, e.g. providing a predictable response or sending flexibility bids. The cost varies depending on the starting point of the site and the objective of the communications [32]. Notice that for participation in some manual programs, such as interruptible program, a conventional smart meter is enough.

2. Computation (OPEX): Variable cost that depends on the degree of automation desired and the amount of data needed to feed the algorithms used by the DA or the EMS. The cost could be concentrated on one actor (the DA) in case of centralized control or distributed among different EMSs otherwise.
3. Transaction (CAPEX): Includes the costs of collecting information regarding products and customers, managing contracts, and procedures for external transactions [33].
4. Activations (OPEX): Defined as the cost to activate flexibility in the site. In the case the flexibility activation in an industrial site implies a reduction in industrial production, the activation cost can be very high [34]. On the contrary, if the flexibility activation reduces the HVAC consumption, the activation cost is null, since it does not bring any economic loss to the building owner.
5. Penalizations (OPEX): Whenever the flexibility provider (or its representative) does not provide the flexibility requested, it incurs in a penalization.

Although it is possible to treat the flexibility provider and the demand aggregator as the same entity, costs and revenues are distributed differently depending on the business model adopted. There are many possible business models; three extreme examples are presented below, focusing on where the cloud computing is.

1. Manual activations without intermediary: This is the simplest case; the flexibility provider has a bilateral contract with the SO or BRP. The activation is manual, through e-mail or SMS. Here the computation effort is low and concentrated at the SO level and there are low communication costs. All revenues and eventual penalizations go to the final user.
2. Aggregator as a financial intermediary: The SO organizes a competitive flexibility market. If a minimum bid size is needed, small participants need to be aggregated and represented as one. In this case, the EMS needs to forecast the flexibility and make a bid to the DA, which sends the offer to the SO. Most of the computational effort is on the EMS level because the aggregator is just the financial representative. In this case, communications costs are higher since it needs an advanced EMS and computation costs fall into the user level. Penalizations for not accomplishing the offer should be charged to the final user too. A big share of revenues should go to the final user since the DA has fewer risks being just the intermediary. In this case, the optimization is at the user level without coordination among final users, losing potential opportunities in contrast to coordinated optimizations.
3. Aggregator as a physical intermediary: the SO organizes a competitive flexibility market as in (2). However, here the aggregator is in charge of the whole aggregation process, from market bidding optimization to real-time flexibility management. Communications costs are lower in this case than in the previous case because EMSs are simpler and just need to read and send measures to the DA. The

computation effort resides on the DA side since it forecasts, optimizes, and manages a big amount of installations. The DA optimizes all assets together, since it knows the potentiality and the status of all the assets, maximizing the common benefit. In this case, penalization should fall into the aggregator and revenues should be higher for the aggregator than in previous models.

As a consequence, computational efforts might take place in any of the three levels (commercial, user, and assets) and at all three levels simultaneously depending on the business model structure. To avoid having local computers with high computing needs in different locations, the use of cloud computing with only a task manager such as a SCADA (Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition) in place is advisable.

This study presents two alternative approaches: the one used in the research SABINA project and the one followed by the Bamboo Energy spin-off.

3. From research in "SABINA"

SABINA is a research project H2020 (www.sabina-project.eu) following a centralized-competitive approach categorized in the Nash Bargaining Game. In SABINA, the DA acts as a price taker and, consequently, the optimization problem goes downstream, that is, from the DA to the buildings and their flexibility assets only.

The direct control over flexibility assets was already tackled in literature [35,36]. Furthermore, in the first stage, most residential building owners would probably decide to install an EMS pursuing energy efficiency to save energy and money. With this hypothesis, this project counted on EMS devices to access the building's energy flexibility by simplifying the computational efforts of the DA.

To do so, SABINA developed a system based on two-level algorithms to manage intrinsic and extrinsic flexibility [37]. At the user level, an EMS is in charge to manage and monitor the energy flows of all the electric equipment and the flexibility assets in a building. The whole SABINA system is done in a way that the EMS should not necessarily be in the same building and could be independently there, in a supercomputer managing several buildings at the same time or in the cloud. What the building should have on site is a SCADA to activate the flexibility assets when the EMS indicates so according to the parameters or setpoints marked by the EMS. Note also that it is the SCADA that manages the real-time energy flows in case of unexpected changes.

For that, the SCADA uploads system information on the flexibility assets of each building into a common platform. Then, the EMS is capable to read the needed parameters of each building from the cloud to optimize their consumption and forecast their available flexibility per hour for the next 24 h. As some buildings were equipped with renewable power generation systems, the EMS needs weather information to forecast the electricity production from these power sources too. This information is also available in the cloud from a service provider. Once the optimization is performed, the EMS uploads back to the cloud the information that the SCADA should use to run the equipment in buildings, fixing the setpoints to use for the next 15 min. This process is recurrent and repeated every quarter of an hour, so the EMS is constantly adapting the setpoints of the equipment according to the deviations it might observe in the equipment during these 15 min and updating its optimization results. All the details about the neural network used by this EMS are accessible in the work by Schubnel et al. [38].

Similarly, the EMS uploads into the cloud the information needed by the algorithm running at the commercial level, the

Market Integrated District Algorithm (MIDA), which is a 3 module algorithm (optimization, execution, and evaluation as in [39]) explained in detail by Canals Casals et al. [40]. This information is:

1. *The flexibility Map.* It refers to the forecasting of three possible demand curves of the building: the optimized demand curve or baseline, which is what the building is expected to follow if there is no flexibility activation from the MIDA; the maximum demand curve; and the minimum demand curve. The difference between the optimized curve and the high and low-demand curves represents the available flexibility the building can provide.
2. *Rebound effect.* For each maximum and minimum demand values per hour, the EMS also publishes information on the deviations in the demand of the building for the following 24 h caused by the flexibility activation assuming that this activation occurs. This is used by the MIDA to calculate the rebound effect any activation might cause in the building and identify when to ask for new flexibility activations with an acceptable uncertainty range.

In parallel, the MIDA uses the information from the electricity grid related to prices and its mix to calculate the environmental footprint (CO₂ emissions per kWh) and publishes it in the cloud to be used for its calculations.

The optimization problem the MIDA solves is to minimize the environmental footprint of buildings (shown in the simplified Eq. (1)) by determining when it is better to activate (h) and how much (β) of the available flexibility (Flex) of each building (i) in the district without representing any additional cost. This optimization also considered the rebound effect (Reb), understood as the need for the building to readjust to the optimal baseline consumption after the activation, and uses the hourly electricity mix (Mix_h) at every instant to calculate the consequent emissions [40]. The Δ index indicates downward activations (increase consumption), while the ∇ index indicates upward activations (decrease consumption).

$$\begin{aligned} MinEmissions = & Min \sum_{h=1}^{24} \sum_{i=1}^n ((\beta_{\Delta ih} \cdot Flex_{\Delta ih} - \sum_r Reb_{\Delta ih}) \\ & - (\beta_{\nabla ih} \cdot Flex_{\nabla ih} + \sum_r Reb_{\nabla ih})) \cdot Mix_h \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

This is done once per day and the MIDA uses the results during the following day to activate the flexibility in case there is any request from the grid level. When a request arises, the module in charge of executing the activation in MIDA asks all buildings that were preselected in the optimization result for that hour frame to update their flexibility capability. This update is necessary to improve the accuracy of the coordinated action. Since the optimization is done during the day ahead, the MIDA is "blind" in terms of energy flexibility, meaning that the MIDA is capable to analyze if the building's portfolio follows the expected baseline consumption but unable to evaluate the impact in the energy flexibility of these deviations for each building. Then, each building reports the amount of energy it can provide. This value should always be equal to or below the set-point marked by the MIDA (which is the same value the EMS indicated the day ahead) with a 500 W higher margin.

Due to computational efforts caused by the neural network-based algorithm used in SABINA's EMS, the updated response from the EMS takes between 3 and 14 min to be published into the shared platform.

After 15 min, the executing module in MIDA allocates all the flexibility by confirming the request to deliver the updated amount of energy by each EMS beginning with the buildings

having a higher reliability index. The reliability index is a value that refers to the EMS accuracy of each building's flexibility estimation. The better the accuracy is, the higher the reliability index. These confirmations for flexibility requests are launched until the total amount of flexibility the grid asks for is fulfilled, leaving the rest of the buildings unaffected and, consequently, without any reward for their contribution, reason why having a good reliability index is important.

These requests are then collected by each EMS to calculate the setpoints of all the manageable loads per building. This information is published in the platform and each SCADA in the building is in charge to transfer them to the devices it controls.

The process described takes 30 min from the moment it receives an activation of flexibility from the grid operators until it effectively begins to deliver this request. It is, indeed, a high latency, which is hard to reduce because of the 15 min cycle defined and the computation time of the EMS.

Moreover, due to this limitation in time reactivity, once the request is accepted by the building, there is no way to react if a building does not effectively provide the agreed amount of energy.

It is during this activation period and afterward (for the rebound effect), that the evaluation module in MIDA evaluates the overall performance of the activation by analyzing:

1. *The flexibility activation:* To understand how close the whole building response was to fulfilling the grid's request.
2. *Baseline curve:* Comparing the baseline curve estimated by the EMS to the actual consumption (this process is done every hour).
3. *Flexibility estimation:* Comparing the value given by the EMS during the day ahead estimation with the value given during the daily update when an activation arises.
4. *Flexibility delivered:* Comparing the value given by the EMS after the flexibility estimation update and the flexibility that the building has provided. This is calculated considering the baseline consumption curve estimated 1 h before the activation, which is what the building should have consumed if no activation was requested. This value is the one foreseen to be used to pay for the service given by each building

Then, these elements analyzed are used to reward the building owners for the service and to update the reliability index. Note that, even when the building has no effective request, the index is updated because the baseline curve is shared in the platform each hour.

In terms of communications, SABINA counts on the same three management layers depending on the element that is ordering downwards (the MIDA, the EMS, or the SCADA), which are closely related to the actor's layers but that, depending on the configuration, could be located in one or several of these levels. To exemplify the information flow between them, a case scenario with a district comprised of two buildings including an energy system for each one is described. The solution is optimized through the output from the EMS and MIDA. The scenario includes:

1. Two buildings: They both count on the same PV station and meteorological data but one has a controllable heat pump and the other one has a Li-ion battery as well as the thermostats in the different dwellings of the building.
2. EMS and MIDA to optimize the operation of the building and the overall district.
3. A SCADA for each building that transfers the commands from the EMS to the controllable devices. It is responsible for communicating and supervising all assets, as well as directly controlling them and storing/sending their key data.

Fig. 2. Concept and information flow in the SABINA solution scenario.

4. Central broker for information exchange between subsystems.

Fig. 2 illustrates the general concept, where the SABINA solution box is located in the cloud, and the building district box, where one finds the SCADAs, which are physically located in the buildings.

The building district transfers information on the state of the systems in the buildings (measurements) to the central broker of the SABINA solution. At the building level, the EMS will manage flexibility by controlling heat pumps, batteries, water tank temperatures, and room temperatures of the buildings (control actions). At the district level, the MIDA will use input from the market and the EMSs to manage the flexibility of several buildings. The SABINA central broker, through which subsystems communicate among them, will handle the information between components. Note that subsystems send messages to the broker, which is responsible for distributing them to other subsystems that subscribe to this kind of messages.

As shown in Fig. 2, there are two communication flows. One concerning the internal communications in Buildings led by the SCADA and the other concerning the SABINA broker.

The communications within buildings are hardware dependent and use protocols like Modbus TCP. The ex-changed data is saved in SCADA tags, which are the basic variables obtained from communication with devices, from the results of calculations, or from the user input. They can be Booleans, integers, real numbers, or strings, and maybe multidimensional. Moreover, tags can refer to a class, which is a customized structure of data, i.e. class members. These members may also behave like tags. Tags are usually linked with one or more registered addresses of a connected asset. The connection is facilitated by a communication driver.

On the other block, communications with the central broker are based on the Internet of Things (IOT), used for the communication between the SABINA solution in the cloud and the other modules. The central controller hosts a Mosquito MQTT broker with enabled security and a core broker database. SCADAs located in buildings connect to the broker and act as gateways between assets and the central Broker. The EMS, MIDA, and Market Interface Weather Forecasts subscribe to the broker to get and send data internally.

Fig. 3. Docker solution adopted.

4. To business in “Bamboo Energy”

“Bamboo Energy”, Bamboo hereafter, created by the same researchers in SABINA, is the software platform for the operation of demand response flexibility aggregation [41]. Bamboo offers a holistic solution to allow energy retailers to take advantage of the flexibility of their clients and became demand aggregators. As such, Bamboo’s clients are energy retailers and not final users. This means that Bamboo maximizes the benefit of the retailer’s portfolio. For that, Bamboo wants to minimize the costs described in Section 2.

Business as usual for DA consists in having a (large) portfolio of consumers and managing their flexibility to participate in different electricity markets. Conventional DA use to focus on a specific segment of consumers [31]. One of the differentiations of Bamboo is that, thanks to the machine learning algorithms implemented, it can manage almost all types of flexible assets simultaneously (HVAC, batteries, industrial processes, etc...).

Depending on the contract between the retailer and the final user, benefits are distributed among all customers. Following the definition in Section 2, Bamboo implements a Stackelberg Game since it has no information on the contract between the retailer and the consumer. The information available for Bamboo is the comfort and operational preferences of consumers, to be respected at all times. For example, in the case of managing an HVAC, Bamboo respects the comfort temperature chosen by the building’s owner. In the same way, in the case of managing an industrial process, Bamboo assures the expected production of the industry and the times of interference.

The algorithms developed are flexible enough to be able to include sites with and without EMS installed. In the case the site has not EMS integrated, it is necessary to install a gateway or SCADA able to send data to Bamboo’s Application Program Interface (API REST) and execute consumption set points at the asset level, like in [20]. If the site has an EMS installed, Bamboo communicates directly with the EMS. In the case the EMS can follow timely the Bamboo flexibility requests, although Bamboo knows the status of the flexibility assets and what can ask for, it is the EMS who decides how to manage the flexibility activation among different assets, as in [23] or in SABINA.

The Bamboo flexibility platform performs all the functions needed for demand aggregation, from the day ahead forecasts to real-time operations. Its main functionalities are:

1. Load forecast (*Predify*): Day-ahead consumption forecast with hourly updates, to estimate the baseline consumption.
2. Flexibility forecast (*Flexum*): Flexibility forecast of different appliances such as industrial processes, HVAC, or batteries.
3. Market bidding optimization (*Bambooptime*): Optimization of the bidding strategy in different electricity markets to maximize profits and assure value stacking.
4. Real-time management (*Realflex*): Management in real time of all the flexible appliances considering the consumer’s comfort and operational constraints.
5. Data analysis and assessment: Analysis of data and evaluation of KPIs for each site.
6. End-user interface (*Bamboolize*): Visualization of indicators, historical data, and forecasts to improve end-user engagement and awareness about electricity consumption.

The platform has an API that allows storing and exchanging data with end-users. All data are stored in the cloud following the solution shown in Fig. 3.

Weather historical data and forecasts (temperature and irradiation) of the locations are stored in Influx and taken from a specialized weather forecast application using their API. In the same way, market data such as electricity prices are stored in Influx too from the marketplace API. Similarly, data gathered from smart meters and sensors installed in the sites are stored in the Influx database.

Time series data are contained in an Influx Docker, separated from relational data stored in MySQL.

The MySQL database is divided into 4 layers, which are, again, related somehow to the actors’ levels defined in Section 2. The first layer is the Bamboo’s customer (the energy retailer) and groups all the buildings within its portfolio. In this way, the system assures independence and privacy among different clients, since data are separated between them. The second layer indicates the name of “the prosumer”. This second layer is not essential neither for privacy, nor for the well-functioning of the algorithms, but it is useful for the end-user interface to group all the buildings owned by the same holder and for future versions of the product. The third layer represents the site itself. Here Bamboo stores static information such as the location of the site (to connect this site with the closest weather station available), the electricity tariff applied, the type of machine learning model

Fig. 4. Information flow and interactions among modules in the Bamboo architecture.

used to forecast the consumption, etc... In the last layer, called "Microgrid", all the information about the assets is stored. From the Microgrid, it is possible to understand what are the flexible appliances within the site, their main characteristics, and how they interact among them.

Middleware enables communication and data management between the databases and the different modules of the platform, contained in different Docker containers. Fig. 4 shows the interconnection among the modules, the information exchanged between them, and the frequency of execution.

To reduce the computational effort while maintaining good performances, machine-learning algorithms for load and flexibility parameter estimation are trained once per month. The load forecast module uses weather data, historical consumption (last three months if it is available), and calendar information to train the models for the day ahead and intraday load forecast, which are uploaded in the MySQL database. Every day, the forecasting algorithm uses the weather forecasts and the historical consumption from Influx to predict the consumption of the site for the next day, which is stored in Influx. This forecast is updated hourly using the last weather and consumption data available.

Bamboo trains the flexibility parameters using weather data and historical data from the site's sensors. The flexibility parameters are stored in MySQL. These parameters allow treating

whatever appliance as a virtual battery. For example, in the case of thermal loads such as fridges or HVAC systems, Bamboo uses an RC equivalent circuit to model the thermal load, like in [42]. Although flexibility parameters are estimated once a month, Bamboo every day forecasts the flexibility available at the consumption site. The flexibility forecast is updated hourly to be visualized through the user interface.

Contrarily to the SABINA approach, the flexibility forecasts themselves are not directly used for bidding optimization or real-time management. The bidding optimization module and the real-time module use the parameters trained in the flexibility forecast module.

The bidding optimization algorithm uses load forecasts, the result from previous bids, market data, and weather forecasts from the Influx database and it takes market characteristics and flexibility parameters from the MySQL database. This module executes the optimization every time Bamboo bids in a market for some of its clients (the retailers) and the optimization is performed separately for each client. This is done because each of Bamboo's clients have a different consumer portfolio and it is seen as an individual flexibility provider by the TSO. The output of the optimization is the volume and price to bid for each period in a specific market.

The optimization problem Bamboo solves is to minimize the energy cost of the different portfolio's consumers, keeping into

account the hourly electricity price λ_h , and the payments prices from the flexibility markets for upward (λ_h^Δ) and downward activations (λ_h^∇) (Eq. (2)). The optimization problem determines when it is better to offer the available flexibility (Flex) of each consumer and is repeated n times during the day to determine the optimal bid for the next market period. The Bamboo's algorithm also considers the rebound effect (Reb) due to flexibility activations. Notice that the price for upward and downward flexibility activations is different, while the energy price to consider for the rebound effect is the electricity price from the consumer's tariff.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Min} \sum_{h=1}^{24} \text{costs}_h = \text{Min} \sum_{h=1}^{24} \sum_{i=1}^n & (Flex_{\Delta ih} \cdot \lambda_h^\Delta - Flex_{\nabla ih} \cdot \lambda_h^\nabla \\ & - (Reb_{\Delta ih} - Reb_{\nabla ih}) \cdot \lambda_h) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The real-time algorithm needs to be fast enough to comply with the technical requirements of the flexibility market. Depending on the flexibility service delivered, the maximum time of response allowed is between some seconds and some hours [7]. Limitations in control or communications speed and ramp-up or ramp-down of some industrial processes could be limiting factors for the participation in fast frequency regulation electricity markets. Depending on how fast the response has to be, Bamboo performs a mathematical optimization or not. In the case of the secondary reserve, which is the faster service delivered by Bamboo, the algorithm uses, as input data, the portfolio's consumption set point indicated by the SO, the consumption measures from the smart meters, and the flexibility parameters and appliances' characteristics. The algorithm checks if communications are working properly and calculates the flexibility available for each appliance. Finally, it allocates the flexibility needed to reach the set point fixed by the SO proportionally to the availability of each installation. If the EMS is in charge of the operations on the site, Bamboo just sends the site's maximum or minimum consumption to reach, while in the case no EMS is installed, Bamboo directly controls the individual appliances.

In parallel, as an additional service, Bamboo checks if the site is respecting the limitation on the maximum power contracted with the DSO to avoid grid charges penalizations. In the case a site is overpassing the maximum power contracted, Bamboo automatically sends a load reduction signal to the site. All the set points sent to the appliances are stored in the Influx database and the consumer can visualize it from the user interface.

The user interface represents the visual connection between Bamboo and its clients. There are two user interfaces for the Bamboo platform users: one for the retailers and the other for the site's occupants. It is web-based and users can enter using their ID and password to check for their data. The retailer's user interface shows the electricity market and operational data. Customers can visualize in real-time how their portfolio is following the signal of the SO, to check the benefits cumulated during a certain period, and have information about the offers and activations made in different electricity markets.

Consumer's user interface shows the current and forecasted consumption, the flexibility forecast of the site, indications about where the electricity consumed comes from (self-consumption, battery, or grid), and what appliances are currently consuming electricity. Users can set alarms to receive through SMS or e-mail to be notified about e.g not expected consumption patterns or flexibility activations.

5. Comparison of the solutions

This section aims to analyze the pros and cons of the DA strategies followed by SABINA and Bamboo in the pursuit of rapid

Table 1

Saaty's preference scale between criteria and the final weight.

Criterion	i	ii	iii	iv	v	vi	Weigh
i	1	0.5	0.25	0.5	0.17	0.14	4%
ii	2	1	0.33	1	0.25	0.2	7%
iii	4	3	1	3	0.5	0.33	16%
iv	2	1	0.33	2	0.5	0.4	10%
v	6	4	2	4	1	1	29%
vi	7	5	3	5	1	1	34%

deployment to market and to understand the reasons that pushed both developments to go in one direction or another.

The comparison is done employing the multi-criteria decision tool through the weighted product model (WPM) scoring method [43], in which values are defined through the AHP. This process is commonly used in project management to decide between different strategies.

The first issue is to define the criteria that will be used to identify which of the alternatives suits better for the purpose, which are described as:

- (i) Amount of information and historical data: the number of different items and the number of times these items are sent between flexibility assets and DA, plus the amount of data needed so the system works in optimal conditions.
- (ii) DA computational effort: Time needed to compute, once all the information needed is gathered, the bidding strategy and the flexibility allocation.
- (iii) Response velocity: Real-time module that allows for a reaction once the flexibility is requested and activated.
- (iv) Responsibility if the response: Who is the maximum responsible for the behavior of the response.
- (v) Uncertainty: Closeness of the expected or commuted flexibility availability with what occurs.
- (vi) Closeness to market: Existence or not of external and uncontrollable issues needed to massively deploy the solution, such as third-party investments or developments.

The second step is to determine the weight of the criterion in the decision matrix depending on the final goal. In this study, the goal is that the DA should rapidly get into business. The value of weight for each criterion is obtained through Saaty's preference scale that relates the relevance of each criterion against the other criterion and their values go from a value of 1 to 9 (as in previous works [44]), considering that they have the same relevance or if the first one is of extreme importance in comparison to the other respectively. These values (Table 1) are then normalized and their average ends up with the weighting factor (last column of Table 1) for each criterion.

These values are validated with the consistency method, having a ratio of consistency of 0.09, which is below the 0.1 established limit [45].

Following the AHP [46], the third step is to evaluate each alternative (Bamboo and SABINA presented in Sections 3 and 4) for these criteria. This is done through the decision matrix, giving a value between 1 and 5 on each criterion of the alternatives analyzed. How these values from 1 to 5 correspond to each criterion is described in Table 2:

Consequently, the decision matrix shown in Table 3 presents *iii*, *v*, and *vi* as the primary criteria, those having higher weight. The ratings of both solutions (SABINA and Bamboo) in all criteria are also visible, where a value of 1 is understood as non-desirable and a 5 as a perfect solution. Acceptable solutions are those having an overall value of 3 or higher and the selected solution should be the one with a higher value.

Table 3 shows how SABINA gets a better rating in half of the criteria but it is Bamboo the solution that receives a better overall

Table 2
Saaty's preference scale between criteria and the final weight.

Criterion	1	2	3	4	5
i	A lot	More than average	Average	Less than average	Almost none
ii	A lot	More than average	Average	Less than average	Almost none
iii	Slow	Slower than average	Average	Faster than average	Very fast
iv	DA	DA and partially EMS	Shared	Mostly the EMS	The EMS
v	A lot	More than average	Average	Less than average	Almost none
vi	Vert far	Far	Average	Close	Under installation

Table 3
Decision matrix to evaluate both solutions.

Criteria	Weight	SABINA	BAMBOO
(i) Amount of exchanged info + Historical data	4%	4	1
(ii) DA computation effort	7%	5	2
(iii) Response velocity	16%	1	4
(iv) Responsibility of the response	10%	3	1
(v) Uncertainty	29%	1	5
(vi) Closeness to market	34%	1	5
Value		1.60	4.06

result (4.06) as it focuses on the most relevant business-oriented criteria. It is correct, then, to follow this approach to create the spin-off.

A better explanation of the rating of each criterion for both approaches is done in the following paragraphs.

For (i) the volume of information exchanged can directly affect communication and computation costs. SABINA gets a good rate (4) as the information exchanged between the EMS and the MIDA is relatively low and concentrated in punctual moments. Remember that they occur during the day ahead (flexibility map and the rebound effect of the building), when a flexibility activation is requested (EMS updates the flexibility map, and then the MIDA sends the flexibility activation to the EMS) and after the activation (the MIDA reads smart meter measurements to evaluate the response of the building). Moreover, it does not need many historical data. On the other hand, Bamboo needs more detailed information, since it is in charge of making the flexibility forecasts and activating in real-time all the flexible resources. This is done at the asset level, which means that Bamboo has to collect data from all flexible assets (batteries, HVAC, etc.) to obtain the lowest possible rating 1. Using the bamboo approach, since the DA estimates all the parameters for the load and flexibility forecast, it needs historical data to train the models (at least 1-month of data). To diminish this impact, this problem can be mitigated by using estimated parameters from similar buildings during the first months every time a new building enters the portfolio

For (ii), the bidding computation time is important for the scalability of the solution since if the computation time is slow, the problem could become intractable. Having fewer and already treated information (flexibility map and rebound effect), SABINA's time response is faster giving it the best rate (5) as it proved to work with 500 buildings without any problem. The slower bidding computation time is found in Bamboo as it considers the assets' characteristics and eventual rebound in the bidding problem. However, Bamboo runs a separate optimization problem for each one of its clients and future developments contemplate clustering to reduce the size of the problem.

However, more important than the computation time of the bidding optimization problem, which can be relatively slow without affecting the DA business, is the response velocity in real-time (iii). A slow real-time reaction could mean closing the possibility to participate in some fast-response services, which usually are more lucrative [47]. The double check in the SABINA approach (as it relies on the information from the EMS) strongly conditions the real-time response velocity. Moreover, once the activation is launched, the MIDA has no control over how accurately the

building performs (v) and, thus, no reaction or reallocation is possible. This implies that, possibly, the risk of falling into penalization is higher than in Bamboo's approach. For these reasons, SABINA receives the lowest rate possible in both velocity ((iii) and uncertainty (v). Bamboo's approach to real-time flexibility management is straightforward. When a flexibility activation arrives at the DA, which is continually ingesting new data from different appliances, it computes the flexibility available at the site level. Then, Bamboo sets the site's flexibility activation proportional to the ratio between the site's flexibility available and the total portfolio's flexibility. Finally, it sends the new consumption set point to the site's EMS (similarly to SABINA but not relying on the EMS forecasting methods) or directly to the asset. Bamboo has a perfect knowledge of what the asset should do and its time response. In the hypothetical case that a flexible appliance is not responding properly due to, for example, a communication problem, Bamboo eliminates this flexible appliance from the equation and modifies the flexibility request to the rest of the customers to adjust the response to the new situation, the reason why it receives the high rating in these two criteria (iii and v).

Closeness to market (vi) is badly evaluated in SABINA as it needs to wait (if ever) for an EMS capable to construct the described information structure of flexibility maps or similar expressions as done by the EMS. This type of EMS is not yet in the market and adapting current EMS would take time and its launching price would be higher than the competition. Since the computational effort and the intelligence in the Bamboo approach resides on the DA side and not on the individual EMS, the adaptability of Bamboo to a different type of EMS is higher. When facing the real world, it is all of the interest of the DA to reduce the investments and modifications to current systems installed in the sites to rapidly increase its portfolio and market operation. This means that the Bamboo solution requires smaller investments for the end user since the objective is to be hardware agnostic, or at least to require the minimum modifications possible to existing EMS. This is what makes Bamboo a solution ready to enter the market.

Given that the EMS in the Bamboo approach has any responsibility for the goodness of the solutions, eventual penalizations from the SO should not be charged to final users and they fall completely within the DA, reason why it receives the worse rating (1) in (iv). Contrarily, in SABINA, the MIDA and the final user share the responsibility for not responding correctly to the SO request, the reason why the rating is in the middle (3).

6. Conclusions

There are multiple ways to confront DR and DA in the current state of technology but none of them is capable of satisfying all relevant issues that facilitate their massive deployment.

This study presents two different approaches. One focuses on easing the computational needs and replication of the DA from a research project (SABINA), and the other is oriented to the market that plans a deployment considering the technological state of the art and the market integration reality (Bamboo). The two approaches are evaluated using the decision matrix proposed in Section 5.

Bamboo's solution is closer to the market. The DA strategy is based on current EMS possibilities and has a fast response to unexpected events, which enables its clients to participate in multiple energy markets simultaneously. As Bamboo's algorithms know and consider the limitations of current Energy Management Systems, the overall investment is relatively low. However, it uses many centralized computational resources, requiring information such as historical data and real-time measurements. Moreover, it is responsible for the good operability of the system, which means that, in case of errors, penalties will fall into the DA.

On the other side, the DA in SABINA's approach needs less historical data, since the EMS is in charge of computing the available flexibility and managing flexibility activations internally. Therefore, it is faster in the bidding procedure, but it relies on a sound EMS to control the building's performance. However, using this approach it is difficult to follow up on the flexibility activation, and expected penalizations from the SO for not respecting the flexibility activation would increase. This same difficulty in the use of evolved EMS is what forces to discard cooperative or user-oriented configurations presented in the literature.

Therefore, in the nearby future, direct access to the flexibility assets using cloud computing in a system-oriented configuration is the road to follow, as demonstrated by the apparition of Bamboo and the multiple positive responses offered by the market and potential customers. However, research should continue the analysis of any other possibility to update businesses or to change the orientation in case of the evolution of the market towards distributed intelligent services, such as evolved EMS with higher services.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

M. Barbero: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **L. Canals Casals:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **A. Colet-Subirachs:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Software, Writing – original draft. **J. Salom:** Funding acquisition, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **C. Corchero:** Funding acquisition, Investigation, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Validation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Lluç Canals Casals reports financial support was provided by Horizon Europe. Cristina Corchero, Mattia Barbero, Jaume Salom, Alba Colet reports financial support was provided by Horizon Europe. Cristina Corchero, Jaume Salom reports a relationship with Horizon Europe that includes: funding grants.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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